

INCIDENTAL DETECTION OF WILSON'S DISEASE DURING METHOTREXATE THERAPY FOR PALMOPLANTAR PSORIASIS IN AN ADOLESCENT MALE: A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

An 18-year-old male receiving methotrexate for palmoplantar psoriasis was incidentally detected to have isolated indirect hyperbilirubinemia during routine follow-up. The absence of hemolysis and the presence of only minimal ultrasonographic changes in the form of grade I fatty liver warranted further evaluation. Biochemical investigations demonstrated reduced serum ceruloplasmin levels and increased hepatic copper concentration, leading to the diagnosis of Wilson's disease despite the absence of classical clinical manifestations. The patient was initiated on zinc acetate along with ursodeoxycholic acid and was placed under continued neurological surveillance. This case highlights the importance of a systematic diagnostic approach when interpreting abnormal liver function parameters in young patients undergoing long-term immunosuppressive therapy. **Written informed consent** was obtained from the patient for publication of this case report.

KEYWORDS: Wilson's disease; Methotrexate-induced hepatotoxicity; Palmoplantar psoriasis; Indirect hyperbilirubinemia; Adolescent.

1. INTRODUCTION

Methotrexate is commonly employed in the treatment of chronic plaque and palmoplantar psoriasis owing to its immunomodulatory and anti-inflammatory effects. Despite its proven efficacy, long-term methotrexate therapy is associated with potential hepatic adverse effects, making regular monitoring of liver function tests essential.

Wilson's disease is an inherited disorder of copper metabolism transmitted in an autosomal recessive pattern. Mutations in the ATP7B gene impair biliary copper excretion, resulting in progressive copper accumulation, predominantly in the liver and central nervous system. The clinical spectrum of Wilson's disease is highly variable, ranging from asymptomatic biochemical abnormalities to advanced hepatic or neuropsychiatric involvement.

We describe an unusual case in which Wilson's disease was incidentally diagnosed during routine monitoring of a patient receiving methotrexate for psoriasis, emphasizing the need to consider underlying metabolic liver disorders in young individuals with unexplained hepatic abnormalities.

2. CASE PRESENTATION

An 18-year-old male with palmoplantar psoriasis presented for routine follow-up while on oral methotrexate (X mg once weekly) for X months, along with folic acid supplementation. Routine biochemical investigations revealed an elevated total bilirubin level of 2.04 mg/dL, with a direct bilirubin value of 0.5 mg/dL, suggestive of isolated indirect hyperbilirubinemia.

The patient was asymptomatic and denied jaundice, fatigue, abdominal pain, or features suggestive of hemolysis. Haematological evaluation, including peripheral smear examination, reticulocyte count, and lactate dehydrogenase levels, was within normal limits, thereby excluding hemolytic etiologies. Abdominal ultrasonography revealed grade I fatty liver, while transient elastography (FibroScan) demonstrated no evidence of hepatic fibrosis (F0).

Further evaluation showed reduced serum ceruloplasmin levels of 13 mg/dL (reference range: 20–35 mg/dL). Twenty-four-hour urinary copper excretion was within normal limits. Family screening revealed decreased ceruloplasmin levels in the father (11 mg/dL) and borderline values in the sibling (20 mg/dL). Slit-lamp examination did not demonstrate Kayser–Fleischer rings.

A liver biopsy was subsequently performed. Although rhodanine staining was negative, quantitative estimation revealed elevated hepatic copper concentration of 118 µg/g dry weight (reference range: 5–50 µg/g), confirming the diagnosis of Wilson's disease. Neurological examination and assessment did not reveal any abnormalities.

Methotrexate therapy was discontinued, and the patient was initiated on zinc acetate 50 mg three times daily along with ursodeoxycholic acid 300 mg once daily. He was advised regular follow-up with dermatology, hepatology, and neurology departments.

3. DISCUSSION

This case illustrates the diagnostic complexity encountered when suspected drug-induced hepatotoxicity coexists with an underlying metabolic liver disorder. Although methotrexate-associated liver injury is a recognized adverse effect, isolated indirect hyperbilirubinemia in the absence of fibrosis or inflammatory changes is not a typical presentation of methotrexate-induced hepatotoxicity.

Persistently reduced serum ceruloplasmin levels combined with elevated hepatic copper concentration raised strong suspicion of Wilson's disease. A hepatic copper concentration exceeding 100 µg/g dry weight, together with low ceruloplasmin levels, fulfills established diagnostic criteria for Wilson's disease, even when urinary copper excretion remains within normal limits.

The absence of Kayser–Fleischer rings and neurological manifestations supports the diagnosis of early-stage hepatic Wilson's disease. This case highlights the broad phenotypic variability of the disorder and reinforces the importance of thorough evaluation of abnormal liver parameters in adolescents and young adults.

Early identification and initiation of zinc therapy are critical in preventing disease progression to cirrhosis or neuropsychiatric complications. Also this case emphasizes the need for vigilance when interpreting liver function abnormalities in adolescents on long-term systemic therapy. Furthermore, family screening and genetic counselling are essential components in the comprehensive management of inherited metabolic liver disorders.

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